

Cross-Platform Conversion Framework for XR in Technician Education

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About RECITE

Led by Impact Allies, the Resource Collaborative for Immersive Technologies (RECITE) seeks to improve STEM technician education through the accelerated integration of cutting-edge extended reality technologies into technician classrooms.

The partners in the collaborative are:

- CA2VES (NSF ATE Center)
- CAST
- Clemson University
- EARTH (NSF ATE Center)
- Motlow State Community College (MSCC)
- Somerset Community College (SCC)
- St. Cloud State University (SCSU)

To learn more about the project, visit recitexr.org.

Table of Contents

Cross-Platform Conversion Framework for XR in Technician Education.....	1
About RECITE.....	2
Glossary of Key Terms.....	4
Executive Summary.....	6
Background and Context.....	6
The RECITE Approach.....	7
Conceptual Design of the Framework.....	7
Development Process.....	10
Challenges and Solutions.....	11
Outcomes and Next Steps.....	12
Conclusion.....	13
Recommendations.....	14
For Developers:.....	14
For Educators and Instructional Designers:.....	14
For Institutions and Funders:.....	14
Appendix A: Cross-Platform Conversion Workflow Guide.....	15
Appendix B: References.....	16

Glossary of Key Terms

360-Degree Video: A form of immersive media that captures a panoramic environment view, allowing users to look around in all directions. Typically used for passive or semi-interactive experiences.

AI-Assisted Development: The use of artificial intelligence tools to aid in code generation, refactoring, optimization, and testing, streamlining the development process.

Augmented Reality (AR): A technology that overlays digital information onto the real-world environment, typically using a smartphone or AR headset.

Behavioral Blueprints: Abstract representations of user interactions and logic flow that can be mapped onto various platforms or scripting languages during conversion.

CFIR (Consolidated Framework for Implementation Research): A framework used to assess and guide the implementation of innovations in complex settings, applied in RECITE's qualitative research on XR adoption.

Cross-Platform Conversion: The process of adapting digital content or applications so they function consistently across multiple hardware or software platforms.

glTF (GL Transmission Format): An open standard file format for 3D models, developed by the Khronos Group, optimized for efficient transmission and loading.

Head-Mounted Display (HMD): A wearable device that provides an immersive visual and audio experience by displaying XR content directly in front of the user's eyes, typically used in VR and MR environments.

Immersive Technology (XR): A broad category encompassing virtual reality (VR), augmented reality (AR), and mixed reality (MR), designed to simulate or enhance real-world experiences.

Interoperability: The ability of different systems, devices, or platforms to work together and exchange information seamlessly.

Middleware: Software that serves as a bridge between different systems, platforms, or applications, enabling communication and translation across XR environments.

Mixed Reality (MR): A hybrid environment where physical and digital objects co-exist and interact in real time, often involving more advanced spatial mapping than AR.

Modularity: A design approach that separates a system into independent, interchangeable components, allowing for easier updates and customization.

OpenXR: A royalty-free, open standard by the Khronos Group that provides high-performance access to XR platforms and devices.

Pseudocode: A simplified, human-readable description of a program's logic or algorithm that is not bound to a specific programming language.

Virtual Reality (VR): A fully immersive digital environment experienced through head-mounted displays (HMDs), isolating users from the physical world.

WebGL: A JavaScript API for rendering interactive 2D and 3D graphics in a web browser, often used as the foundation for browser-based XR experiences.

WebXR: A web API that allows developers to create immersive content (VR and AR) accessible directly through web browsers, without the need for platform-specific applications.

XR Interaction Toolkit: A Unity toolkit designed to facilitate cross-platform development of interactive XR applications with a consistent input system.

Executive Summary

The Resource Collaborative for Immersive Technologies in Education (RECITE) is a National Science Foundation Advanced Technological Education (NSF ATE) special project focused on accelerating the adoption of immersive technologies, virtual reality (VR), augmented reality (AR), and mixed reality (MR), within technician education. As RECITE supports the development and implementation of open XR educational resources, a critical challenge has emerged: the fragmentation of XR platforms limits the accessibility and usability of these resources across different devices and ecosystems. This white paper presents a cross-platform conversion framework designed to enable developers to adapt XR content developed for one platform into formats compatible with others. This initiative aims to increase the longevity, reach, and educational impact of XR resources by reducing technical barriers and promoting interoperability.

Background and Context

Immersive learning offers opportunities for differentiated instruction and accessibility accommodations, including multimodal content delivery, adjustable interaction speed, and customizable user interfaces. However, these benefits are often not fully realized due to platform constraints or the lack of inclusive design practices (W3C, 2023).

In the context of technician education, XR technologies provide uniquely powerful tools for experiential learning, skills practice, and simulated troubleshooting in safe and scalable ways. For example, students can explore virtual equipment models, complete step-by-step repair procedures, or observe simulated system failures without requiring access to costly or hazardous physical resources. XR in technician education spans a wide range of formats - from browser-based WebGL applications and desktop simulators to fully immersive head-mounted display (HMD) environments. Additionally, augmented and mixed reality experiences are increasingly being deployed via mobile devices or AR glasses to support real-time, on-site learning in classrooms, workshops, and field environments. Other approaches include the use of interactive 360-degree video for storytelling and scenario-based instruction, particularly where real-time rendering is not required.

Despite this potential, the field faces persistent limitations in cross-platform compatibility. XR content developed for one device or toolchain (such as Unity targeting Oculus headsets) often cannot be reused on others (like mobile AR or WebXR environments) without extensive redevelopment. This has led to fragmented content ecosystems and significant rework burdens for educators and developers. Additionally, many educational XR projects are not optimized for accessibility or resource-constrained contexts, further exacerbating inequities in adoption.

While some open educational resources (OER) exist, they are often created with proprietary tools and tied to specific platforms, making them difficult to share, customize, or maintain. As part of RECITE's mission, there is a pressing need to document and disseminate a structured, replicable process for converting XR resources across platforms and expanding their usability in technician education contexts.

The RECITE Approach

RECITE - the Resource Collaborative for Immersive Technologies - is a grassroots initiative composed primarily of educators, supported by an NSF ATE special project. Our mission is to explore, document, and support the implementation of XR technologies in technician education with a strong emphasis on practicality and reuse. Unlike many top-down or theory-driven efforts, RECITE is grounded in the experiences of practitioners who are actively integrating immersive tools into classrooms, labs, and training environments.

Our network includes community colleges, technical institutions, and industry partners, many of whom are experimenting with XR in diverse ways - from desktop simulations to HMD-based training scenarios and mobile AR field tools. Rather than beginning with a formalized needs assessment, RECITE's early work involved qualitative inquiry rooted in the Consolidated Framework for Implementation Research (CFIR), which helped us understand real-world barriers and facilitators to XR adoption. These include infrastructure constraints, institutional support, user readiness, and the perceived value of immersive learning outcomes.

What sets RECITE apart is our commitment to "doing" over theorizing. We aim to produce replicable, open solutions that help educators and developers share, convert, and deploy XR content more effectively. While the conversion framework outlined in this white paper is still in its early stages, it represents a critical step toward systematizing the often fragmented, ad hoc efforts that characterize XR development in education. By centering the needs of implementers, and drawing directly from field experiences, RECITE is building a foundation that others can refine, adopt, and grow over time.

Conceptual Design of the Framework

The conceptual framework guiding RECITE's approach to cross-platform XR content conversion is built on three core principles: interoperability, modularity, and sustainability. These principles were identified based on the recurring technical and instructional barriers faced by XR implementers in technician education. Each principle addresses a crucial pain point: interoperability responds to platform fragmentation; modularity supports reuse and versioning; and sustainability ensures XR content remains viable as technologies and educational contexts evolve.

Interoperability means ensuring that XR experiences can function consistently across devices such as desktops, head-mounted displays, mobile AR platforms, and web browsers. This is crucial in technician education, where learners may be accessing content from a variety of institutional or personal devices. The framework leverages platform-agnostic standards like glTF for 3D assets, the WebXR Device API for browser-based delivery, and OpenXR for consistent device access.

Modularity promotes the separation of content into reusable components, such as 3D models, user interaction scripts, UI elements, and instructional metadata. This allows developers and educators to update, customize, or replace components independently. For example, a digital multimeter model can be reused across lessons or upgraded without modifying interaction scripts or user guidance.

Sustainability refers to the ease of maintaining, updating, and distributing XR resources over time. Modular design supports sustainability by isolating changes, while open standards reduce reliance on proprietary formats. Sustainability is especially critical in educational settings, where curricula and delivery platforms often change over multi-year cycles.

The framework is implemented through a four-layered architecture:

1. **Content Abstraction:** Ingests and standardizes source materials (e.g., glTF, SVG, JSON). Ensures assets are separated from platform-specific containers.
2. **Interaction Logic:** Defines how users engage with the content. Abstract behaviors are described using templates and mapped to specific scripting languages.
3. **Platform Translation:** Middleware and scripts handle the differences between rendering engines, control schemes, and input/output systems.
4. **Deployment Packaging:** Platform-specific build tools generate outputs suitable for each device type and include accessibility metadata and documentation.

Each layer interacts with AI-enhanced tools that assist with translation, code optimization, QA testing, and documentation. This architecture allows contributors to operate within their domain of expertise: developers focus on code, educators review interactions, and instructional designers ensure alignment with learning goals. The layered approach also fosters collaboration between roles without requiring every team member to master every tool or standard.

Software Architecture

Figure 1 Layered architecture of the RECITE Cross-Platform Conversion Framework showing the modular workflow from content abstraction to deployment packaging.

Long description:

The figure presents a four-layered diagram depicting the software architecture of the RECITE Cross-Platform Conversion Framework.

- Content Abstraction (top layer): Standardizes source materials, such as 3D models, media, and metadata, into open formats like glTF and JSON.
- Interaction Logic (second layer): Defines how users engage with content, using templates or pseudocode that can later be implemented in different scripting languages.
- Platform Translation (third layer): Handles rendering, input systems, and device-specific configurations for platforms such as WebXR, mobile AR, and immersive headsets.
- Deployment Packaging (bottom layer): Assembles the final builds, including accessibility metadata and documentation, for release across multiple environments.

Arrows connect the layers vertically to represent workflow and interdependence. Feedback loops indicate that updates in lower layers may inform revisions in higher ones, illustrating the iterative nature of the framework's development process.

Development Process

The development process of the cross-platform conversion framework is structured around five iterative and interrelated stages. These stages provide both a conceptual roadmap and a practical workflow for developers and collaborators to follow. Each phase is designed to support modular contributions and decision-making based on technical constraints, pedagogical goals, and implementation contexts. For the purposes of this framework, all development and testing are conducted in Unity. While Unreal Engine offers powerful development capabilities, it no longer supports WebGL export, which limits its accessibility for browser-based deployment and educational distribution. Unity's continued support for WebGL and its robust XR Interaction Toolkit make it the most appropriate engine for ensuring cross-platform compatibility and open dissemination

1. Pre-Conversion Analysis begins with a comprehensive assessment of the existing XR experience. Developers catalog all source assets - 3D models, animations, shaders, scripts, audio, UI components - and evaluate their current platform dependencies. Instructional designers may also participate at this stage by clarifying the intended learning objectives and core interactions, ensuring that essential pedagogical elements are preserved during conversion. Teams identify target platforms, note hardware limitations, and flag potential gaps in accessibility or compatibility.

2. Asset Modularization focuses on disassembling content into portable, reusable components. Developers convert proprietary formats into open standards like glTF for models and OGG/MP3 for audio. UI assets are reformatted using vector-based (SVG) or data-driven (JSON) schemas. Metadata such as asset roles, usage context, and instructional tags are attached at this stage. This modular approach enables assets to be reused in multiple lessons, updated independently, and shared with minimal rework.

3. Interaction Mapping transforms the logic of user interaction into delivery platform-agnostic (Meta Quest, Vive, WebGL, executable) schematics/specifications. This includes behaviors like object manipulation, navigation, or UI triggers. Developers use flowcharts or pseudocode to express logic before implementing it in the scripting language of the target platform (e.g., C# to TypeScript). AI tools can assist by auto-generating code snippets, flagging missing logic, or optimizing structure. Collaboration with educators ensures that learning goals remain intact, especially where interactivity or assessment is central.

4. Platform Translation adapts the modular assets and interactions to the conventions and capabilities of the target platform. Developers adjust rendering settings, input systems, and control schemes to match the expectations of desktop, web-based simulation, mobile AR, or immersive HMD environments. Middleware may be used to abstract platform differences, and fallback strategies are employed where features are unsupported. This phase often requires close collaboration between developers and QA testers to ensure behavior is consistent and performant.

5. Validation and Packaging involves comprehensive testing and final assembly of the XR experience. Testing should be conducted on all intended devices to verify performance, usability, and accessibility. Standards such as WCAG 2.1 and Section 508 are applied to assess captions, screen reader compatibility, and interaction alternatives. Final builds are created using platform-native packaging tools, and documentation is updated to include versioning, compatibility notes, and known limitations.

AI tools can enhance every phase of this process, from streamlining code conversion and metadata tagging, to simulating user flows and generating test scripts. While these tools do not replace human judgment, they serve as force multipliers, helping teams move faster and with greater consistency.

To make this workflow more accessible and actionable, RECITE has developed an accompanying [Online Conversion Tool](#) that guides users through the framework in an interactive, browser-based format. The tool prompts users to describe their application's features, frameworks, and key components, then specify the source and target platforms. Based on these inputs, it generates a tailored conversion guide aligned with the five-stage process: pre-conversion analysis, asset modularization, interaction mapping, platform translation, and validation. By translating the framework into a dynamic interface, the tool helps educators, developers, and designers apply cross-platform principles without deep technical overhead, supporting broader adoption and consistent implementation across the XR ecosystem.

This structured approach ensures that XR content developed for technician education can be adapted efficiently across multiple delivery environments while maintaining instructional fidelity and technical robustness. See Appendix A for the detailed checklist.

Challenges and Solutions

Implementing cross-platform XR solutions in technician education presents several persistent challenges. These include technical disparities between platforms, inconsistent user experiences, limited accessibility, and the absence of standardized development workflows. In many cases, XR content is developed with a single device or engine in mind,

such as Unity for Oculus - and must be painstakingly reworked to function on WebXR or mobile AR. Rendering differences, inconsistent support for input modalities, and hardware limitations frequently lead to usability issues or incomplete feature sets.

One of the most prominent challenges is maintaining fidelity of experience across varied hardware. High-end headsets might support hand tracking and spatial audio, while mobile AR may require simplified visuals and tap-based interaction. Without deliberate design strategies, such disparities can result in significantly different learning outcomes. The framework addresses this by encouraging developers to adopt baseline feature sets that function across all platforms, with enhanced experiences layered in where supported.

Another major challenge lies in the translation of interaction logic. Input systems vary widely, from controller-based interactions and touchscreens to gesture-based interfaces. Developers often need to rethink user flow or control design entirely when moving between platforms. The framework's use of behavioral blueprints and pseudocode supports this process, and AI tools can streamline refactoring across languages and environments.

Toolchain fragmentation also poses a challenge. Each platform may require unique SDKs, packaging tools, and debugging environments. The framework's layered architecture and modular asset handling help reduce this complexity by encouraging standards-based development (e.g., glTF, WebXR, OpenXR) and consistent documentation.

From an organizational standpoint, barriers include limited developer capacity, lack of institutional training in XR, and difficulty fostering collaboration between educators and technical teams. The framework mitigates this by offering shared language and role-based workflows, allowing instructional designers, developers, and subject-matter experts to contribute without requiring deep platform knowledge.

Finally, there is a persistent challenge around sustainability and long-term maintenance. XR tools evolve rapidly, and content can become obsolete when platforms deprecate features or alter input APIs. The framework's emphasis on modularity and open standards minimizes rework, and its AI-assisted documentation approach supports ongoing updates.

In sum, this framework does not eliminate the inherent complexity of XR development, but it offers practical strategies to manage it. By formalizing best practices, supporting open standards, and integrating AI where useful, RECITE's framework provides a roadmap for broader, more equitable implementation of immersive technologies in education.

Outcomes and Next Steps

While the cross-platform conversion framework is still early in its lifecycle, its development has already yielded important insights and foundational tools for future adoption. Initial pilot

testing and iterative design work have demonstrated the framework's potential to reduce rework, increase modular reuse of XR assets, and enhance accessibility across diverse delivery platforms. These outcomes affirm the need for a structured, replicable method of cross-platform conversion in technician education.

As RECITE moves forward, the next phase involves deepening collaborations with educators, developers, and institutional technology teams. We will continue refining framework components, particularly documentation tools, asset templates, and AI-assisted conversion scripts, based on community feedback. Another priority is developing sample applications and shared content repositories to illustrate the framework in action and provide reusable resources for adoption.

Dissemination will include formal research outputs in academic venues, as well as open access tools and guides available through the OEXR Library. This online portal will provide implementation case studies and serve as a feedback loop for iterative improvement. We will also explore partnerships with standards bodies and tool vendors to align the framework with emerging XR ecosystem trends.

The work ahead is ambitious, but it reflects RECITE's core philosophy: that immersive educational content should be reusable, portable, and accessible to all learners - regardless of platform, setting, or institutional resources.

Conclusion

The RECITE framework represents a pragmatic response to the complex, fragmented XR ecosystem currently confronting educators and developers in technician education. Rather than prescribe a one-size-fits-all solution, the framework provides a flexible, standards-based approach that acknowledges the diversity of platforms, learning goals, and technical skill sets in the field. It empowers teams to convert and deploy XR content more efficiently, while preserving educational value, accessibility, and long-term maintainability.

By centering the framework on modularity, interoperability, and sustainability - and integrating AI tools where they offer genuine support - RECITE offers a path forward for institutions seeking to invest in scalable, inclusive immersive learning. Though still in its early stages, this framework reflects a growing movement: one that values action, transparency, and community-driven innovation over siloed development or theoretical idealism.

Our goal is not simply to produce guidelines but to build a shared foundation others can refine and extend. With continued collaboration, testing, and open exchange, we believe this

framework can contribute meaningfully to a more adaptable and equitable future for XR in education.

Recommendations

For Developers:

- Design using open, modular standards to future-proof XR content.
- Follow the checklist in Appendix A to guide efficient conversions.
- Leverage AI tools to assist in iterative, test-driven development.

For Educators and Instructional Designers:

- Collaborate early to define learning outcomes and evaluate usability.
- Provide accessibility feedback during testing.
- Share classroom implementations to support best practices.

For Institutions and Funders:

- Fund professional development in XR and inclusive design.
- Build infrastructure for versioning, authoring, and accessibility compliance.
- Promote open-access publishing and collaborative development.

Appendix A: Cross-Platform Conversion Workflow Guide

This section outlines detailed instructions for each phase of the cross-platform conversion workflow, offering practical guidance and strategic considerations for developers.

Pre-Conversion Analysis Begin by performing a comprehensive audit of all assets and technical dependencies. This includes cataloging 3D models, textures, animations, scripts, audio files, and UI components. Document the development environment, including tool versions, SDKs, and plugins. Evaluate each asset's compatibility with cross-platform standards such as glTF, JSON, and WebXR. Define the target platforms and their limitations - such as input types, rendering capabilities, and hardware constraints—to guide all downstream decisions.

Asset Modularization Break down content into modular, reusable components. Convert proprietary 3D models to glTF, standardize audio to common formats like OGG or MP3, and transform UI assets into scalable formats like SVG or JSON. Where applicable, extract and annotate metadata, including tags for asset type, educational context, and usage notes. This modular structure facilitates efficient reuse and simplifies future updates.

Interaction Mapping Translate user interaction logic into platform-agnostic blueprints. Start by describing core behaviors in narrative or flowchart form. Then, map these behaviors to the scripting environments of the target platforms (e.g., C# in Unity to JavaScript in WebXR). AI tools can assist by generating syntax-specific code, optimizing logic trees, and identifying translation inconsistencies. Ensure input modalities (e.g., hand tracking, controllers, mouse) are appropriately mapped across environments.

Platform Translation Adapt rendering and performance features to the new platform context. Optimize shaders, lighting, and animation pipelines as needed. Integrate with platform-native toolkits, such as the XR Interaction Toolkit or WebXR API, to align interaction and input systems. Where features can't be replicated directly, develop fallback behaviors or simplified alternatives and document these thoroughly.

Validation and Packaging Test functionality and user experience on all intended platforms and devices, including HMDs, mobile, and desktop. Validate accessibility compliance with WCAG 2.1 and Section 508 for captions, screen reader compatibility, and input navigation. Use platform-specific build systems (e.g., Unity Build Pipeline, Webpack) to package applications for deployment. Document all build settings, version changes, and known limitations to ensure future maintainability.

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